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Reception Policies, Practices and Responses

Iraq Country Report

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List of abbreviations

HHRO: Hammurabi Human Rights Organization

IDPs: Internally Displaced Persons.

IOM: International Organization for Migration

MOMD: Ministry of Migration and Displacement

UNHCR: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

UIMS: United Iraqi Medical Society

WFP: World Food Program

MSF: Medecins Sans Frontiers (Doctors without Borders)

DAFI: Albert Einstein German Academic Refugee Initiative

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Project Summary

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit, and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyze governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative that is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization. Each thematic field is reflecting a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and responses by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). This report is concerned with the findings related to WP4, which focuses specifically on reception policies, practices and humanitarian responses to the current refugee crisis.

Executive Summary

This report is a study of the process of receiving refugees and displaced people in Iraq, specifically in terms of Iraqi legislation and policies, and the their implementation in regard to institutions and actors involved in the refugee reception processes for the period of 2011-2017. It also aims at discovering the extent to which Iraqi legislations and policies have been adapted and harmonized in accordance with the spirit and provisions of the Iraqi constitution, the rules of international law with regard to reception conditions, and human rights standards.

The term reception here means the conditions and support which should be provided for asylum applicants so that they can access housing, food, clothing, health care, security, education for children, work, an adequate standard of living, etc. Despite the fact that the timeframe for "reception" is not clearly defined in international and regional legislation, there is an implicit period that starts from the time the asylum seeker crosses the border of a specific country and submits an application for international protection and ends either by accepting the request for protection or expulsion for those who fail to obtain asylum status. In this context, the scope of our report can be summarized as follows:

- Introducing the legislations, regulations, and systems in Iraq regarding the reception process.
- Illustrating of the reception policies, practices, and the extent of the humanitarian response to them.
- Presenting the perceptions, and experiences of actors at the refugee level (micro) and at the level of national and international organizations (meso), in other words, policy implementers and their beneficiaries with regard to reception.
- Determining and evaluating the level of humanitarian response to refugee flows and patterns.
- Assessing the nature of the work and coordination of governmental and non-governmental institutions and other actors concerned with the reception, as well as the extent of cooperation between federal, regional and local institutions in this context.
- Identifying the challenges and providing solutions and recommendations within the framework of policies related to the reception process.

Therefore, the objectives of this report can be summarized as follows:

- To develop a mapping of policies and practices of reception in the countries being researched
- To develop a typology of these policies, practices and responses
- To assess the coherence of these policies and practices with respect to international standard
- To study migrants' perceptions, actions, and reactions to policies and practices
- To provide basic information on reception for the development of all subsequent WPs.

1. Introduction

This report investigates the issue of refugee reception, as one of the important issues on which international and regional agreements have focused as a part of refugee protection. It focuses on evaluating the degree to which Iraqi law prioritizes refugee issues, given the fact that Iraq has become a significant receiving country in light of the crises that have beset the Middle East over the past two decades.

This report focuses on the period of 2011-2017, which witnessed the escalation of the Syrian crisis, the return of many Iraqi refugees to Iraq, particularly from Syria and the influx of more than 250,000 Syrian asylum seekers into Iraq.

This report notes that although Iraq has a law for political refugees, it does not have a comprehensive refugee law that regulates the humanitarian, political, social and economic aspects of their conditions, despite the fact that large numbers of refugees arrived in Iraq, especially from Syria, as mentioned above.

This report outlines the following:

- How Iraq managed to organize the refugee reception processes
- The policies, regulations and systems that Iraq followed at the federal, regional and local levels
- How Iraq responded to urgent refugee needs
- How Iraq has been corresponding about the condition of asylum seekers
- The extent to which Iraq has been making efforts to adapt its legislation to better organize and manage the reception of refugees
- The extent to which laws have been reconciled to match the spirit of the Iraqi constitution, international laws, and other international and regional standards.

In addition to that, this report reveals whether or not Iraq has overcome the legal loopholes and filled gaps to provide adequate reception of refugees, despite its unprecedented experience receiving large numbers of refugees within a short period.

Furthermore, the report deals with the way Iraq facilitated the reception in areas deemed safer for internally displaced people who were affected by sectarian conflicts and violence between 2005-2007, and affected by the continuing violence during the past ten years, which escalated in 2014, and resulted in one third of Iraq being occupied by ISIS, and the displacement of more than three million people.

2. Methodology

The researchers used an inductive method to draft this report, through which they collected data on international and regional laws, customs, conventions and treaties related to the protection of refugees, and generalized the subject (case) of Iraq (the situation) with regard to laws, agreements, customs and international treaties specific to refugees, that is, the link between the Iraq case study and the international (general) refugee situation. Meaning, to study the reception situation of refugees in Iraq as part of the whole situation and rely on, in analysis, the information derived from the interviews conducted by the research team at the micro level with refugees, meso level with organizations, regional and international agencies, and also on the macro level with government entities responsible for managing the displaced and refugees file.

The comparative approach was used in parallel with the inductive approach in this study. The national reception in Iraq was also identified by collecting information and analyzing data from interviews with refugees and displaced persons, conducted by the research team.

The team conducted 29 interviews with Syrian refugees: 26 of which had Kurdish origin and 3 were from other minority groups such as Assyrians, Christians, or others. 16 of the refugees were male and 13 were female. 17 arrived in Iraq between 2011 and 2014, while 12 arrived during the period of 2014 -2017. They were distributed to three governorates in the Kurdistan region: 14 to Erbil, 11 to Duhok, and 4 to Sulaimaniyah. The interviews included 17 refugees between the ages of 18 and 38 years (9 males and 8 females). From the age group of 39 to 59 years, 5 were males and 4 were females, and from the age group of 60 and above, 2 were male and one was female.¹

As for interviews with internally displaced people, there were 29 interviewees total, 14 of which were male and 15 female. 9 represented non-Muslim religious minorities such as Yazidis, Christians, and others. 25 were displaced between 2014 and 2017 and 4 between 2011 and 2014. The interviews also included three age groups (18-38) years, which included 5 interviews with males, 6 with females and ages (39-59) included 6 males and 8 females, and ages 60 and above included 3 males and 1 female². The field team also held two meetings with meso level actors and several meetings at the level of decision makers at the macro level.

¹ See table 1

² See table 2

3. Policies and Legal Regulations of Reception: A Multi-level Perspective

Iraq, having received 249,000 Syrian refugees between 2011 and 2015, took in the fourth largest number, only behind Turkey (1.9 million), Lebanon (1.1 million) and Jordan (629,000).³

Our concept of reception in this report is defined by all activities and services provided to refugees, beginning from the moment they cross the Iraqi border until their legal status is resolved.

The Iraqi legal system lacks a clear process for the reception of refugees, and therefore Iraqi executive authorities have resorted to issuing decisions. Thus, with the beginning of the flow of Syrian refugees into Iraq, the Council of Ministers issued, at its 32nd session, on 24 July 2012, a decision⁴ that agreed on the following:

- Establishing camps in the appropriate border areas (Al-Qaim and Rabeaa) and preparing all service requirements there.
- Representatives from the Ministries of Defense, Interior, Transportation, the Iraqi Red Crescent and Nineveh and Anbar governorates will be added to the Emergency Cell for Iraqi Returnees and Syrian Refugees that was already created by the Council of Ministers. The ministries will be responsible for supporting the efforts of the Ministry of Displacement and Migration and relevant national committees.
- Allocating fifty billion dinars, equivalent to USD 41,666,666, from the 2012 emergency reserve to the Ministry of Displacement and Migration to fund the grants for Iraqi returnees from Syria and to secure the requirements of Syrian refugees, including transportation, as per the instructions of the Ministry of Displacement and Migration.

In 2013, the Iraqi government made significant contributions to support the activities of the UNHCR for Syrian refugees in Al-Qa'im (Anbar Governorate) and the Kurdistan region.⁵ With the growing role of the United Nations in helping Iraq, the UNHCR took the largest burden of receiving and managing refugee camps in Al-Qa'im and the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement gradually withdrew from it.

3.1. National Policies and Regulations

From 2011-2017, there were complications surrounding asylum seekers in IDPs in Iraq. In 2014, ISIS occupied one third of the Iraq and displaced approximately 4.1 million people⁶. With the flow of refugees across Iraqi borders, whether within the Kurdistan Region of Iraq or Anbar province, the Iraqi government found itself in need of legislation to regulate, receive and protect refugees.

³ www.radiosawa.com on 9, September 2015.

⁴ The Republic of Iraq, cabinet secretariat, decision No. 32 of 24/7/2012 www.cabinet.iq...show.aspx?id=2309&lanq=A

⁵ Iraq: global appeal 2014-2015. www.unhcr.org...nhcr.org/ar/53fae9666.html

⁶ <http://www.unhcr.org/ar/4be7cc27goa.html>

The number of IDPs and refugees reflect the suffering and tragedy that international organizations and Iraqi government agencies (federal and regional) faced. For example, UNHCR were concerned about the following number of IDPs in respective years.⁷

2016 5,326,166

2017 4,501,786

2018 3,092,425

Therefore, on 28 December 2017, the government sent a draft refugee law to the parliament, which included 19 items aimed at regulating asylum rules in Iraq (humanitarian, political, or other cases) in accordance with the Iraqi constitution, law, and structural and administrative system.

This draft was not passed in parliament primarily due to a controversial provision that would have allowed foreigners citizenship after ten years of residency in Iraq, (some MPs even suggested that it be five years).⁸ It was suspected that political motivations were behind this provision, as there were Kurdish refugees from Iran, Turkey, and Syria in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq and there were Saudi and Bahraini (Shi'a) opponents in Najaf city.

The Refugee Law was not passed and the only existing law concerning political refugees was Law No. 51 of 1971⁹ which does not make clear reference to the process for receiving and governing refugees, Also, the law of the Ministry of Migration and Displacement does not include a clear reference to how refugees to Iraq are received refugees except what was stated vaguely in paragraph 7, article 2 of this law, which reads:

The ministry aims at taking care of those covered by the provisions of this law, from the following category (displaced and deportees, Iraqis returning home, refugees and asylum seekers who live outside Iraq because of the forced migration and have obtained permanent residence or acquired the nationality of a foreign country, Palestinian refugees, refugees to Iraq from other nationalities); assisting and providing them with required services in all essential fields; and making efforts to find solutions to remedy their situations in accordance with the law".

As for paragraph 7, it defines the refugees as "those who have sought asylum Iraq from other nationalities as a result of being persecuted or because of race, religion, nationality, belonging to a certain social group, political opinions, or as a result of exposure to violence in general or events that seriously disturb public security threatening their lives, physical integrity, or freedoms, and those whose asylum has been accepted in accordance with international law and agreements to which Iraq is a party."¹⁰

3,402 refugees entered Iraq through the Al-Qaim border crossing and were registered by Iraqi authorities in July of 2012. . The Council of Ministers granted them residency for a

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Parliamentary division over legislation to delay the resolution of the cases for 3,000 foreign refugees, see: www.almadarpaper.net, also see Al-Mada newspaper, issue 4449 on 15/6/2019.

⁹ Iraqi Laws and Legislation, Iraqi House, Iraqi Laws / p4952 www.dorar-aliraq.net.

¹⁰ Law of the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement No. (21) of 2009, al waqaea al Iraqi newspaper, No. 4141 on 11/11/2010

period of six months, which could be extended, and in order to receive them appropriately, the cabinet approved the following:

- Establishment of camps in the appropriate border areas and prepare all requirements for them
- Representatives from the Ministries of Defense, Interior, Transportation, the Iraqi Red Crescent Nineveh and Anbar governorates will be included to the Emergency Cell for Iraqi Returnees and Syrian Refugees which is responsible to follow up the Refugees and IDPs requirements led by the minister of Migration and Displacement Ministry.
- The ministries are responsible for supporting the efforts of the Ministry of Displacement and Migration and the relevant national committee
- Allocating 50 million dinars, equivalent to USD 41,666,666, from the 2012 emergency reserve to the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement to cover the grant for Iraqi arrivals from Syria and to meet the needs of Syrian refugees¹¹, including transportation.

Until the implementation of the decision, as an emergency measure, 17 schools in Qaim have been designated for Syrian refugees. Each clan sheikh was assigned the responsibility of one school.¹² The army transferred them from the border via buses that were provided by transportation ministry. They were temporarily accommodated in 17 schools in Al-Qaim, to be managed cooperatively by local authorities in Al-Qaim and Al-Anbar Governorate until camps were established.

The Iraqi tribes in Anbar Governorate contributed to a large extent by providing food, supplies, and blankets, in addition to the three meals a day and 300,000 Iraqi dinars for families (150,000 Iraqi dinars per person) provided by the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement.¹³

As the flow of Syrians continued, an emergency cell was formed by the order of Prime Minister. The Minister of Migration and Displacement or a representative, was made the chairman and membership consisted of relevant ministries and authorities in addition to the UNHCR and the Iraqi Red Crescent. This committee supervised the organization and provision of security, housing, food, clothing, health, and educational necessities¹⁴, etc.

The Ministry of Immigration and Displacement was responsible for housing the refugees. For this, it established three camps in the Al-Qa'im area to accommodate them, after transferring them from schools that were not fit for housing. The ministry of Migration and Displacement sought cooperation from the Department of Agriculture in al Anbar which

¹¹ The Republic of Iraq, Iraqi Cabinet Resolution No. 32 of 24/7/2012, General Secretariat of the Council of Ministers www.cabinet.iq

¹² Ahmed Bassem Mohamed, Refugee Services Division Officer, Immigration Affairs Department, Ministry of Displacement and Migration, Member of the Follow-up Cell at the Border in 2012-2013 Interview on 10/2/2020

¹³ Ahmed Bassem Mohamed, refugee services officer, Immigration Affairs Department, Ministry of Migration and Displacement, Member of the Follow up Cell at border in 2012-2013, Interview on 10/02/2020.

¹⁴ Mohamed Hantok, Ministry of Displacement and Migration, Director of the Immigration Department, interview dated 10/02/202.

allocated land to construct the first camp in the Al-Obaidi area in Anbar, with a capacity of 800 tents, and other service facilities and could accommodate 5,000 Syrians.¹⁵ The camp is 45 km away from the Iraqi-Syrian border in Anbar. The camp was established in cooperation with the High Commissioner for Refugees one month after Syrians started flowing in mass to the Iraqi borders. It was supported by a grant of 1.8 billion Iraq Dinars from the Ministry of Migration and Displacement (MMD) to finance levelling and preparing the ground of the camp and erecting a fence for it.¹⁶ The MOMD also provided tents that can withstand the heat of Iraqi summer. Correspondingly, the Iraqi Humanitarian Relief ISHO (funded by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees) provided the camp with bathrooms, health facilities, and kitchens.¹⁷

As a result of the increasing number of refugees, the MOMD expanded the camp and established a second camp nearby. Subsequently, the activities of the United Nations, represented by the High Commissioner for Refugees, increased built a third camp close to the other two. Simultaneously, the World Food Program launched efforts to help refugees.

As for education, the Iraqi government, through the Ministry of Education, has provided primary education within the camps. Therefore, with the start of the Iraqi school season, which usually begins in September, a school has been opened in Al-Qaim camp according to the Iraqi educational curricula and supervised by the directorate of education in Al-Qa'im. Iraqi teachers were commissioned to teach there, and the program benefited from Syrian refugee teachers themselves and the UNHCR undertook the salary payment and benefits of Syrian teachers.

The older age groups received complementary education through contributions of civil society organizations. The Childhood Friends organization, supported by UNICEF, built schools for sports and games for children.¹⁸

The Ministry of Health provided ambulances and paramedics to accompany convoys processions coming to Iraq. A report by the Director of Al-Qa'im Primary Health Care district indicates that the Ministry has sent ten ambulances with ten paramedics to the border crossing in Al-Qaim to follow up on Syrian refugees. The preparation was done before the refugees entered Iraq and aimed at providing emergency services and determine the initial health status of the refugees. In addition to that, fourteen government detachments were opened consisting of a supervising doctor with two medical cadres, an ambulance driver distributed over the border crossing in Al-Qaim as well as the consulting clinic located in the Karabla region and over twelve schools throughout Al-Qaim.¹⁹

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ The letter of the Iraqi Humanitarian Rescue Organization (ISHO), No. 30 / A, on 5/8/2012, addressed to the municipal section of Al-Qaim District, under the title Receipt of Materials.

¹⁸ Ahmed Bassem Mohamed, Refugee Services Division Officer, Immigration Affairs Department, Ministry of Displacement and Migration, Member of the Follow-up Cell at the Border in 2012-2013 Interview on 10/2/2020.

¹⁹ Report of the Al-Qa'im Sector directorate of primary health care on the activities of the Anbar health department in the Syrian refugee camps, on 1/8/2012

The government has also provided medical teams with medical devices, available medicines, medical supplies, medicines for chronic illnesses, sterilizers, disinfectants, and all health, administrative and technical requirements of the work. The report also indicates that Al-Qa'im Primary Health Care district supervised the environmental health within refugee camps in Al-Qa'im and provided advice to workers from other liaising departments and volunteers. A health control committee was also created to supervise the implements of healthy condition in the Sunni Endowment kitchen which prepares the food in the camps. The health care of the district also cooperated²⁰ with UNICEF by providing families with nappy packs and health kits.

Moreover, special forms were prepared for reporting the condition of those who suffer from chronic diseases so that the same quality of treatment could be provided to refugees as that of Iraqi citizens, according to the directives from the deputy minister of health.

The sector has also coordinated with UNICEF to include immunization of age groups included in the national vaccination program. Also, Al-Qa'im healthcare sector developed a systematic program for administering vaccines, according to their age groups. Preparations were also made to implement vaccination campaigns regarding adult vaccines, such as typhoid vaccine, bilateral vaccine, and others. The medical detachments distributed in the refugee camps were able to examine and treat a total of 1,595 people. A total of 105 difficult cases were referred to the Al-Qaim general hospital and 13 cases were referred to the hospitals in Ramadi, the center of Anbar Province.²¹ The Civil Defense Department of the Interior Ministry sent special cars to the civil defense.²²

3.2. Regional and Municipal Policies and Regulations

With Syrian refugees entering Iraq through the Al-Anbar governorate Al-Qaim bordercrossing point, the Emergency Cell Committee for Iraqi returnees and Syrian refugees was formed. It was headed by Dr. Salam Al-Khafaji, deputy of the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement to improve the situation for Syrian refugees and the process for receiving them.²³

The District Commissioner of Al-Qa'im formed a committee to hand over to sponsors Syrian refugees who do not want to remain in the camps, in accordance with security and administrative conditions. For this purpose, forms were prepared in which the sponsor pledges to guarantee the Syrian refugee abides by the law,²⁴ after the approval was given by the security committee consisting of the head of the security committee in the local council for Rawa District, and the membership of the Intelligence Department, Al-Qaim

²⁰ Ibid

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ahmed Bassem Mohamed, Refugee Services Division Officer, Immigration Affairs Department, Ministry of Displacement and Migration, Member of the Follow-up Cell at the Border in 2012-2013 Interview on 10/2/2020

²³ Form (Pledge) No. (50) issued by the District Commissioner of the District of Al-Qa'im, the Committee for the Extradition of Syrian Refugees to Sponsors

²⁴ Look to the form of pledge (commitment) figure 1 in the appendix, and its translation figure 2

National Security Service, Police Intelligence, Army Intelligence represented by 28th Infantry Brigade.

One condition of this sponsorship is that if requested, within 24 hours the sponsor must bring the refugee to the authorities. Moreover, the sponsor must pledge that the refugee will not violate state security and public order. The sponsor must also ensure that the dependent is not affiliated with terrorist organizations and is not wanted by the Syrian courts. Moreover, the sponsor accepts to bear a fine of 10 million Iraqi Dinars, for each day the refugee fails to show up when summoned by authorities. Additionally it was demanded that the refugee must live within the geographical area of the sponsor's residence and is not permitted to move to other governorates .²⁵

Al-Qaim Electricity Department installed a network of lamps to illuminate Al-Qaim camps, powered by the power station in Baiji. The Ministry of Immigration also supplied the camp with electric generators in case of power cuts.

The army and police provided security for the camp, and placed a sand barrier 6-7 metre high around the camps as protection from attacks. The government contracted hygiene services in refugees' schools and government agencies supervised the work.

Also, civil society organizations, clans, mosques, and religious institutions have supported refugees upon their reception. The Iraqi Humanitarian Rescue Organization, the religious authority in Najaf, many clans and individuals distinguished themselves in providing the refugees with food items, blankets, and other necessities.

There are also field visits to follow up on and inspect the health and social conditions of Syrian refugees in reception centers in Al-Qaim. These visits were conducted by the local administrations represented by the member of the emergency cell, a member of the local council represented by Mr. Hamid Nawar and Mr. Ehab Ahmed. The local council monitored the health condition of refugees, provided statistics on patients with diseases, and established treatment controls.

The emergency cell committee distributed grants from the Iraqi government in the amount of 400,000 dinars to Syrian refugee families, which included 350 families as of the drafting of this report. The same emergency cell worked intensively with UNHCR to establish the first camp with 300 tents. The cell coordinated with the local authorities and service departments in Al-Qaim district for logistical purposes regarding the establishment of the Syrian refugee camp. It distributed relief aid of 200 samples and 100 from IOM parcels to 200 Syrian refugee families in Al-Qaim. It coordinated with the International Organization for Migration(IOM) to distribute aids and tents in Al-Qaim. The cell coordinated with the Iraqi Humanitarian Rescue Organization and through the Ministry of Migration and Displacement to provide assistance to Syrian refugees consisting of 50 refrigerators, 50 water tanks, 100 fans, 1,450 water boxes, 2 television sets and provided the site with 4 KV10 generators.²⁶

²⁵ Report of the Al-Qa'im Sector directorate of Primary health care on the activities of the Anbar health department in the Syrian refugee camps, on 1/8/2012.

²⁶ Salam Al-Khafaji, a summary of the report of the emergency cell for Syrian refugees in Qaim and Walid, August, 2012.

Among the main local organizations that provided assistance to the Syrian refugees is the Iraqi Humanitarian Rescue Organization (ISHO), which provided 75 coolers, 100 vertical and chargeable fans, 50 water tanks, 1,450 drinking water boxes, 9 television sets with satellites dishes, a caravan for the mobile health clinic, and 8 million dinars to cover the costs of shelter centers, meals for 612 people and distributing 550 gifts to the refugee children.²⁷ It also provided 68 sanitary facilities, 68 ready-to-be-installed bathrooms in the shelters provided by UNHCR, given that the organization is considered as the executive partner.²⁸

The Department of Electricity in Al- Qaim built a complete electrical grid in the southern section of the Syrian refugee camp to provide lighting. An electrical ration of 30 megawatts has been allocated in camps, but the load reached 40 megawatts due to the spread of refugee centers over a wide area of the district and subdistrict. This led to the reducing the share of electrical energy.²⁹

The security committee consists of the following security agencies³⁰

- Security committee in the local council of Al-Qaim District
- The National Security Department in Al-Qaim
- Al-Qa'im Intelligence Department
- The security committee in the local council for the district of Rawah
- Police intelligence
- 28th Infantry Brigade Intelligence (Military)

The work of the security committee focus on:

- Meeting with the patrols from the army and police who are assigned to the refugee shelters.
- Preventing any member of the security forces from entering refugee shelters.
- Inform all of the security personnel of the necessity of dealing properly with refugees, as they are loved guests in Al-Qaim district.
- Ask all their sources to report the negative and positive incidents that occur in the center.

²⁷ The letter of the Iraqi Humanitarian Rescue Organization (ISHO), addressed to the Municipal Council for the District of Al-Qaim, under the topic of donating, the number 29/1000 on 27/02/2012.

²⁸ Certificate No. 30/1000 of 05/01/2012, the Iraqi Humanitarian Rescue Organization (ISHO), addressed to the Municipal Council of Al-Qaim District

²⁹ The report of the existing electricity distribution department, which is addressed to the list of District Commissioner, No. 158 on 3/8/2012

³⁰ Security situation report submitted to Mr. Salam Al-Khafaji, Deputy minister of Ministry of Immigration and Displacement and Chairman of the Emergency Committee for Syrian Returnees and Refugees , August / 2012.

The Anbar Traffic Directorate also secured roads that refugees take from the borders to their shelters. It received refugee families from Syria and for that it formed detachments to do this task, consisting of traffic officers and employees.³¹

3.2.1. In the Kurdistan Region of Iraq

The Kurdistan Regional Government has relied on the experience of the United Nations and its specialized agencies to receive refugees in the major waves of asylum. The United Nations, in cooperation with the KRG and other specialized parties, established the refugee camp in the Shukran district of Erbil province to reduce pressure on the other camps at that time.³² Especially since the only camp early on was in the Domiz region in Dohuk. IOM also contributed to organizing easy and safe migration by moving migrants from the borders to the camp and non-camp sites.³³ The Kurdistan region has received 233 thousand refugees in nine camps since 2012, with 4 camps in Dohuk which are Domiz, Domiz 2, Kwilan, Akre Fort and 4 camps in Erbil, which are Dar Shukran, Korkusk, Basertah, Qushtaba and one camp in Sulaymaniyah called Barika. The ability of the Kurdistan Regional Government to deal with refugees was subjected to severe pressure, especially during periods of major influx as the situation in Syria intensified. For example, on August 18th, 2013, about 10,000 Syrian refugees entered Kurdistan via the Fishkhapur and crossed the bridge on the Tigris River. Just two days prior to that, 7,500 refugees entered Iraq through the Kurdistan region, which caused great difficulties for the Kurdistan Regional Government, United Nations agencies and NGOs to deal with this flow.³⁴

The Save the Children charity launched a campaign to distribute essential items to refugees who were waiting to register with United Nations bodies. The head of the emergency team (Alan Paul), stated once:

This is an unprecedented flow of refugees, and our first concern is that many of them are stuck at the borders in Iraq or in reception centers that lack the necessary services, adding that "Iraq's ability to deal with refugees is basically under intense pressure, so children who have been "borne" from calamities constitute what a child should not be "enduring." They are almost half the number of refugees.³⁵

According to preliminary assessments conducted by the IOM field team in Iraq in August 2013, refugees coming to Iraq were of diverse demographics. They included about 70% families with children, including a number of families headed by women, about 30% individuals and 10% elderly, 3% handicapped, the majority of whom are Kurds, and most of them were exhausted and vulnerable when they reached the border.³⁶

³¹ Anbar Traffic Directorate letter - administrative affairs personnel department No. 2829/1000 on 24/07/2012

³² Thousands of Syrian refugees influx to Iraqi Kurdistan, August 18, 2013, www.bbc.com...q-Kurdistan-Syrian-refugees

³³ Iraq and the Impact of the Syrian Crisis September 1, 2013 www.iomiraq.net

³⁴ Thousands of Syrian refugees influx to Iraq Kurdistan, www.bbc.com. Op.cit

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Ibid.

The Iraqi government recently put in place policies to govern the refugee reception process, as the National Security Council at the session No.6 held in April 2019, and based on the directive of the Council of Ministers meeting session No.5 held on March 5, 2019 and based on the presentation made by the Legal Advisor to the National Security Council regarding the Syrian refugee file, has decided the following:

The legal description for Syrian refugees is as follows:

1. IDPs from the Syrian border region were received for humanitarian reasons due to the crisis in Syria.
2. The Ministry of Migration and Displacement continues registering displaced Syrians in coordination with UNHCR and with Kurdistan Regional Government
3. The Ministry of Interior established a database to record biological information on the displaced Syrians in coordination with the Ministry of Interior in Kurdistan region.
4. The Iraqi Ministry of Interior grants a temporary personal identification card to displaced Syrians in coordination with the Ministry of Interior of Kurdistan Region, provided that the costs of its issuance are covered by UNHCR, based on the Memorandum of Understanding between the Refugee Standing Committee and the UNHCR - Iraq Office.

4. Practices of Reception

The reception process in Iraq happened within a short period of time, particularly in the Kurdistan region of Iraq, where most of the arrivals obtained asylum seekers' documents within a period of one to seven months, and then a residency permit after a protection document as an asylum seeker from the UNHCR.

This qualified them to move from reception and departure centers to urban areas, or to stay in the camps, meanwhile possessing the right to work and commute in and out of camps. The arrivals to the region also had the right to leave the reception centers once they were properly sponsored by Iraqis, or relatives or friends who had previously obtained residency in the region, provided that the sponsorship was approved by the relevant security and administrative apparatus, as mentioned above.

The refugees included a mixed population, the vast majority of whom entered with families with children, and a number of those families were led by women. The arrivals to Iraq also included elderly, handicapped and single individuals. The vast majority were Kurds, and the rest are Arabs, Assyrians, and Yezidis, most of whom are from nearby Syrian cities on the Iraqi border, such as Al-Qamishli, Hasaka, Deir Ezzor, Raqqa, and others. Most of them were exhausted by the time they arrived at reception centers. They were worn out after the long march to reach the borders under very hot conditions in the flaming summer of Iraq, with a lack of refreshments and cold water, or enduring biting cold in the winter, when they lacked adequate clothing and blankets and emergency heating.

In order to understand the process of practices of reception that took place in Iraq within the period of our research in the years 2011-2017, we chose to focus on the following topics:

4.1. Housing in camps and urban areas

The researchers found, through field work, that the places designated for housing refugees (camps) were not prepared in terms of infrastructure; streets, lighting, health facilities, or public services. The religious and ethnic identity of the refugees in Iraq played a major role in determining the direction of residence and housing. Syrian Christian refugees went to Christian villages in Dohuk, such as Bakhtami and Badrash in Dohuk, and the city of Ainkawa in Erbil, while the Sunni Arabs went to Ramadi, at a time when the Syrian Kurds, who are the majority of the Syrian refugees, preferred to reside in the provinces of a region Kurdistan Erbil and Sulaymaniyah and Dohuk. The International Organization for Migration (IOM) estimates that 89% of the Syrian refugees in Iraq are Sunni, 64% of them are Kurds and 25% are Arabs.³⁷

Regarding the lack of infrastructure, a Syrian refugee described how was he received:

After we entered Iraq, we went to camp (Domiz) and there were relatives for us. We were helped by our uncle who had arrived before us. He gave us a tent after staying in his house for a day in Duhok. We worked on getting the required

³⁷ Iraq: The Impact of the Syrian Crisis, Report of the International Organization for Migration (IOM), Baghdad Regional Center, Iraq, September 2013

paperwork with the help of Qandil Organisation and we stayed for four months in the slums of the camp and without electricity and water. (Irq- 4RLM- Micro-Syr- M –No.4).

Another refugee said the following:

We crossed from the border crossing point of Vishakkor, we crossed the bridge on foot, and there was a great crowd. We were (12) people in the family. We could not see each other because of the crowding. Everyone wanted to save himself. We met each other afterward. We reached the Iraqi side, and the journey took two hours almost. Where we took the peshmerga with large trucks packed with immigrants, we were (100) people in the car (like sheep) to Erbil and to the Kuracusk camp, and the camp was near Ain Kawa in Arbil, about a quarter of an hour from Dara Shakra.. When we arrived, we slept on the ground for two days, we did not get any aid or tent and did not work, we didn't even have blankets. (Irq-21PFM - Micro-Syr- F –No.21).

Along similar lines, another Syrian refugee said the following:

After our first arrival, the urgent need for us was housing and shelter, no one helped me in housing, I lived with my cousin. We did not get aid from anyone, not even a tent, so I stayed with others, and that affected and changed my personality and behaviour which affected my relationship with others, and also changed my children's mood as well. (Irq-16SHMB - Micro-Syr- F –No.16.)

As a refugee asserts:

I did not expect the conditions as they were. There were no housing or shelter. Things were unstable and I have been staying in my cousin's house for the past year, which is small and doesn't have enough space even for him. But now I am renting an apartment in Dohuk and our relationship with the camp continues. We rented the apartment with the approval of Asayish. I had an urgent need for accommodation because I was staying with a group of people whom weren't in a good economic condition. All these, in addition to the lack of a work opportunity, which I desperately needed it. (Irq-17AFA - Micro-Syr- M –No.17).

As the refugee says,

I am not happy in the camp. If there is another place, I prefer moving to elsewhere. There are no parks or amusement parks for children here. In my current place of residence, I do not pay rent, I built a room; the roof is made of tin. I built it myself with the help of my friends. No organizations helped me. My in-laws helped me from abroad. The good things about my accommodation is that the neighbours are good, as if we are one family, school and the bread shop are nearby. The bad things are that streets are not paved, the power goes off and water supplies are very little. (Irq-24KJK - Micro-Syr- M –No.24)

While a representative of a civil society organization working with refugees confirms that "the infrastructure is not sufficient to respond to the need of migrants, but there has been an improvement in the Iraq's ability to develop infrastructure in recent years". She adds; "the reception is currently good in terms of infrastructure, funding, and legal provisions, but it needs improvement and maintenance." She emphasizes; "that there are more funds

and more actors, infrastructure has improved, and there are positive changes in legal provisions”.(Irq-1DGHY-Meso- F-No.1)

The centres and camps that were set up for the reception did not absorb the continuous flow of refugees, which forced many of them to leave and seek housing and shelter outside the camp, which led to the refugees having to search for jobs to make a living and the rent. The rent was often high compared to their income, it was clear through fieldwork, that more than half of the refugees live outside reception centres, living mainly in urban communities. One of the refugees confirms:

After we entered Iraq, they took us in buses to a camp in Zakho, which is supervised by the Barzani Charity Organization, then we left the camp in Zakho to Erbil and stayed with my sister in a camp, but later I stayed at my brothers' in Erbil, and I worked for a month before I left my job when the employer closed his shop, then my brother opened a laundry shop from my nephew's money so I worked in the laundry with him, we closed the laundry because of the high rent and opened another one where rent is cheaper, the amount of money I borrowed from my younger brother was paid to my older brother; the laundry owner which was \$1500 USD, then I rented a house for 200 thousand Iraqi dinars where my father, mother, and younger brother lived with me, then I got married in 2017. (Irq-7MSA- Micro-Syr- M –No.7)

It turns out that the majority of Syrian refugees in Iraq are of Kurdish descent. They settled in camps or with host communities across the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, as the authorities in the region facilitated housing approval for families to live outside the camps or to rent, when an Iraqi citizens or a Syrian relative who had previously obtained residency in the region to sponsor a refugee. Individuals without families had difficulty getting approval to rent in urban areas. It was customary for these IDPs to spend a few days or weeks in Domiz Camp or Bardarash Camp in Dohuk before leaving in search of jobs and better living conditions. In this regard, a Syrian refugee says,

We were received by the Peshmerga on the border. They provided us with water and food, provided buses for us, and took us to the Bardarash refugee camp, and we stayed there for 12 days. Then we left the camp through a sponsor, my son (Sherzad) who was in Kurdistan earlier and took us out of the camp, we came to Erbil in Kazanzan area, we rented a house for \$500 for 3 months, then we moved to Mamzada and rented for \$400. (Irq-11SHFH- Micro-Syr- F –No.11)

There were other attractions that influenced the decisions regarding the place of residence. 40% of Syrian refugees have relatives living in Iraq. Therefore, most chose to reside in the governorates where their relatives live or in places compatible with their social or cultural inclinations or their religious affiliations. In addition, the refugees indicated that their decision was affected by the favorable economic and security conditions in the Kurdistan Region, and the availability of work opportunities. As the refugee says:

I was received well by the camp administration, where there are tents for reception, but I did go to it. I went with my relatives in the camp. I came with my relatives. I was acquainted with my friends and relatives (my uncles), my feeling of reception in the beginning was better than it is now. (Irq-20RKA- Micro-Syr- M –No.20)

Another refugee says:

After we crossed, we were transported by the Peshmerga from Fishakhabor to Erbil Erbil by buses, after I got there, I stayed one night homeless in Erbil, then my nephew came and we went to my sister's house in Dohuk in the Alnasara neighbourhood and then I went to the refugee camp In Domiz, I registered, and I followed the procedures to apply for asylum, and they gave me an appointment to follow up in a month, and after my review I was given a document as an asylum seeker... The reception in Iraq was good, but alienation/separation is difficult, but currently it is different because of the basic needs in terms of housing and simple needs for the house, such as paying the rent at the beginning of the month, as well as our need for blankets, food, and kitchen materials. (Irq-22MAR- Micro-Syr- M –No.22)

The new comers from the Syrian refugees were placed in reception camps and temporary facilities, such as schools, mosques, and public centres designated by the Kurdistan Regional Government. In view of the lack of adequate accommodation at the beginning of the crisis and the large number of refugees, improvised camps were established in various parts of the Iraqi border governorates, such as Dohuk and Ramadi, which lacked basic services and necessities for life. The refugees relied on themselves, on what they were carrying on their person and whatever made available to them.

4.2. Access to health and psychological care

The living conditions of the new refugees were poor. The families live mostly in overcrowded primitive housing, lacking sanitary infrastructure, and are exposed to harsh weather conditions, which may increase the spread of dermatological and respiratory diseases. Ahmed Bassem stresses that "some of the refugees who initially entered Ramadi province had viral hepatitis and some of them had dermatological diseases. That is why clinics were opened in the camps by the Directorate of Health of Al-Qaim and there were special visits by a dermatologist doctor, as some cases were diagnosed as skin diseases caused by sunstroke or skin allergy."³⁸

A report from the Emergency Cell Committee to the Undersecretary of the Ministry of Migration and Displacement, the head of the Emergency Cell for Refugees and Returnees stresses "giving medicines for dermatology and full clothing of (men, women, boys, girls, and children) as well as full underwear for men and women and instructing refugee families to wash with sulfur soap and special ointments, changing clothes completely and handing them over to the camp management and changing all refugee mattresses to hand over new mattresses."³⁹

In this context, a Syrian refugee describes his suffering with his children after his arrival, as he says,

After our arrival, my children got hypersalivation, this is a rare disease, as pimples/spots appear on the hands and legs, and the medical service standard here is frankly a failure. I send pictures of medical examination to my mother-in-

³⁸ Ahmed Bassem Mohamed. Ibid

³⁹ A report from the Crisis Cell Committee, addressed to the Undersecretary of the Ministry of Displacement and Migration, under the title Follow-up, on 03/08/2012

law, so she presented it to Syrian specialists in Syria in order to diagnose the disease... The disease of my children is a kind of disease which is transmitted by animals and causes vomiting cases for 14 days, we faced a great difficulty in admitting them to the hospital. There they were injected with nourishment. The transportation fees from my area to the hospital is expensive, it cost 15 thousand dinars, I am without job, and I faced horrors so that I can even get one of my children to the hospital , no one helped me with the treatment. (Irq- 3OMK-Micro-Syr-M-No.3).

Some refugees complained about the lack of medicines, treatments and medical assistance. A Syrian female refugee said "I go to a clinic for treatment and no one helps me. There are not enough medicines in the clinic" (Irq-16SHMB-Micro-Syr-F-No.16).

Another Syrian female refugee said,

I asked for medical assistance from humanitarian organizations, no one met my request, as I requested treatment, medicine and surgery, but my request was rejected when I submitted this in writing (Irq-18MYA-Micro-Syr-F-No.18).

While other refugees confirmed to the field team that they received health attention, stressing that first aid accompanied them after entering Iraq, and that civil society organizations provided them with medical assistance.

A Syrian refugee said, "After we entered Iraq, they provided us with medical assistance with food and services, and received assistance from foreign organizations" (Irq-8APA-Micro-Syr-M-No.8)

Another female refugee confirms,

I am sick with asthma and pneumonia, and because of my illness, I am in need of help. I was given care as a patient and an elderly woman. We received assistance from some organizations at the border as well as by the Peshmerga" adding "the organization MSF (Doctors Without Borders) provided us the aid (Irq-11SHFH-Micro-Syr-F-No.11).

In this context, some Syrian refugee women are spoke about the health care they received. One of them says,

There was a clinic in the camp and health awareness offered by international civil society organizations" (Irq - 13SAA-Micro-Syr-F-No.13). Other adds "We did blood tests and there was an interest in me as a woman (Irq-15LYA-Micro-Syr-F-No.15).

Another refugee says,

When I arrived at the camp after I entered, the camp administration asked me to have a blood test, to find out my blood type (Irq- 24KJK-Micro- Syr-M-No.24).

And it turned out that the Syrian refugees suffered from psychological and physical trauma after they entered Iraq. As a Syrian female refugee confirmed,

This trip affected me at the beginning, I suffered from tension and frustration, but now everything is good and the health is good. Yes, I needed help when I arrived, and my family helped me in times of tension, frustration and depression, especially from my older sisters from me (Irq- 21PFM-Micro-Syr-F-No.21).

Another refugee stresses,

The asylum process affected me psychologically, The thought of finding a job. The lack of mental comfort and the pressure also affected me. Sometimes, I feel depressed. But I have not sought health assistance. The changing circumstances and the work, being absorbed by it, created pressures and effected my psyche negatively (Irq-20RKA-Micri-Syr-M-No.20).

Another Syrian refugee says,

The flight and asylum process affected me physically, as I developed cervical spine disorder, and it affected me psychologically. Sometimes I feel depressed. No one helped me to get out of this situation. I need help, but I did not get any. I calm myself, when I was getting depressed I would go to my neighbors. Sometimes, I would go for a walk outside the house in order to rest, and sometimes I cry and feel relieved. Yes I needed help but did not receive any. I asked a medical committee of MSF (Medicines Sans Frontiers) without getting help or even response from them. (Irq-19EMS-Micro-Syr-M-No.19).

4.3. Access to early education

Through the fieldwork carried out by the research team and the meetings that the team conducted with Iraqi officials concerned with Syrian refugees coming into Iraq through Anbar Governorate which border Syria, it can be noted that "they received care in regard education. Schools for children at primary school age, were opened in Al-Qa'im camp through the Al-Qa'im Education Directorate. they relied on the Iraqi educational curricula. Likewise, non-governmental civil society organizations supported by UNICEF, have opened supplementary schools for children from other stages, and to play games and sports.⁴⁰

In the context of education as well, refugees faced mounting difficulties, but the biggest of which was the issue of language, especially in the Kurdistan region of Iraq, where most of the Syrian refugees live. The language of education there is Kurdish, while most Syrian refugees speak Arabic. Likewise, there are a few schools that use Arabic, and if there are schools with Arabic language in the Kurdistan region of Iraq, they are far from their places of residence. The registration process is not easy, and requires official Syrian documents to be brought in, and many refugees are not able to provide them.

One of the workers in an international organization, self a refugee stresses that

The biggest challenge in Kurdistan region is the language, as the Kurdish authorities refrained from teaching in Arabic in secondary schools. In addition, there is also the problem of equalizing certificates obtained from the mother country or the difficulty of obtaining official documents. UNICEF is strongly involved in primary education programs. We also provide support in teacher training, accelerated education, and the DAFI program... The shortcomings that I suffer from are lack of knowledge of the Kurdish language, and there is a problem

⁴⁰ Ahmed Bassem Mohamed, Ibid.

with schools, because our language is Arabic, studying in Erbil is in the Kurdish language, and Iraqi government schools that teach in Arabic do not accept Syrian students" (Irq-2AFSH- Micro-Syr-F-No.2).

Through fieldwork, it was found that very few of refugees from secondary level conducted their education. As for elementary schooling, there were efforts to reach them, depending on the proximity of the refugees' place of residence. The economic aspect of the refugees played an important role in this aspect.

As a female Syrian refugee said, "During the reception period, no one help me or my children regarding education" (Irq-18MYA-Micro-Syr-F-No.18). Another refugee confirms, "From the time I arrived and until I got the asylum seeker document, I did not get legal advice or any other care, my children are in a regular school." (Irq-12EMS-Micro-Syr-M-No.12)

A female refugee complains because of schools and financial deficiency, "Our shortcomings are that the school is remote, my husband's work is remote, the streets are not paved, and electricity supply is only for three hours per day, and the local generators require money that we cannot afford." (Irq - 27RHH- Micro-Syr-F-No.27).

Another refugee underlines that his children's school is nearby, he said, "The good advantages of my residence is that the school is close and the bakery is close." (Irq-24KJK-Micro-Syr-M-No.24).

Refugees noted that their living conditions and psychological repercussions affected the mood of the children and thus reflected on their desire to go to schools. In this context, a female Syrian refugee states,

I was affected and my personal nature changed and the impacted on my relationships with others. My children's mood has changed as well. I get angry a lot because they do not want to go to schools, and they fight with each other (Irq-16SHMB-Micro-Syr-M-No-16).

4.4. The role of non-state actors in reception

Many sides – federal, regional and municipal government agencies, in addition to international and national organizations, Iraqi civil society organizations, residents and others – have worked and contributed to the process of receiving refugees and asylum seekers from the moment first they entered Iraq from various border crossing point. But the front line of reception was borne by the authorities in the Federal government of Iraq and the Kurdistan Regional Government. A woman working in an international organization asserts,

We can say that we are working on the reception but the front line for reception is the Iraqi authorities for certain. As for the authorities of the Kurdistan Region, they are concerned with those who enter through the port of Fishkhabur and other border crossings there, for those who come through Baghdad airport, after the authorities in Baghdad allow, we support them as soon as they enter – after accepting them. (Irq-2KWV-Meso-F-NO.2).

In this context, Hadeel from UMIS Organization confirms that,⁴¹

With the outbreak of the crisis in Syria, UMIS has set up a camp in the Kilo 18 area and other camps in Anbar to prepare for the reception of Syrian refugees. In general, organizations don't usually respond to individual cases of refugee crossing, but responds immediately and urgently when the concerned governmental authorities gather a number of refugee families in a specific location.

Many of those interviewed, whether at the macro level, the miso or the refugees themselves (the micro), have confirmed the existence of a high-level coordination between non-state actors among themselves and with the state, and there has been cooperation between the federal government and regional and local governments.

As Mr. Mohamed Hantok, director of the Immigration Department at the Ministry of Displacement and Migration, says

Since 2012 there have been several patterns for a rapid response to the refugee influx. The local pattern is like the one that occurred in Al Qaim, which is represented by citizens hosting Syrian refugees in their homes, schools, and mosques. The second type of response is the emergency response that is provided by the Ministry of Displacement and Migration. The third type is the support provided by the UNHCR and other international organizations, as the UNHCR undertook the construction and management of three Syrian refugee camps.⁴²

Mr. Ali Ayoub of UNICEF confirms that

There is coordination between international organizations working in Iraq and each of them is concerned with a specific sector, for example UNHCR is concerned with the protection and registration of refugees and has a presence in the Zammar and Ibrahim Alkhalil crossings in Kurdistan.⁴³

Ms. Hadeel of UMIS highlights the improvement in the coordination between the actors and the increase in their experience in receiving refugees. She says

After 2011, the country's readiness has changed and became more adept in receiving the displaced and refugees. When the largest displacement occurred from Fallujah, there was a lot of confusion in responding to it. Currently all government agencies and local organizations have gained enough experience to respond quickly not only to situations of displacement due to wars and armed conflicts, but in other cases, such as floods and other disasters. coordination has improved between government agencies and local organizations as well, including the use of a referral system to governmental or non-governmental agencies concerned with providing services to refugees or displaced persons.⁴⁴

⁴¹ Hadeel Muhammad, UIMS, Roundtable Meeting on December 15, 2018.

⁴² Mohamed Hantok, previously mentioned source, round table meeting on 15/12/2018

⁴³ Ali Ayoub, UNICEF, round table meeting on 15/12/2018

⁴⁴ Hadeel Muhammad, Ibid

Another activist whom the field team met confirms “There is coordination and partnership, but more coordination mechanisms that respond to urgent and immediate situations is needed” (Irq-1DGHY-Meso- F-No.1).

Regarding the differences in reception policies between the actors at the federal government and the Kurdistan regional government, Sana from UNHCR says

There is a big difference between the different political approaches at the regional and central levels. For example, the approach in Baghdad was to apply the Residence Law to refugees who officially entered Iraq, while the Kurdistan Regional Government was more welcoming.⁴⁵

In this context, Hadeel of UMIS confirms,

The instructions and policies pursued by the Kurdistan regional government are more organized and more in line with international standards. It is often the forerunner in developing and implementing policies and then they are applied in Baghdad.⁴⁶

While Mr. Muhammad Hantouk adds in this regard,

The Kurdistan regional government is more permissive in working with international and local organizations, unlike the situation in Baghdad where bureaucracy and corruption play an important role in obstructing work.

Refugees and IDPs have expressed appreciation for the positive role of the people and tribesmen in assisting them after they entered Iraq, in addition to the role of the state, local and international civil society organizations. In this regard, a Syrian refugee says,

We stayed one night after crossing in a school in Zakho, and then buses came from the Kurdistan Regional Government and took us to Arbad camp near Sulaimaniyah, we stayed there for about a year, and then we moved to Barika camp, since the Arbad camp was designated For Arab and Yazid IDPs... We got support only in terms food. There were a number of organizations and people in Arbad who gave us aid in terms of clothing, mattresses, supplies and bread, but I do not know the names of the organizations or people. I value the role that the people of Arbad played in helping us and all the Syrian refugees, there was a warehouse of the aid provided by the people of Arbad and it includes the necessary items that the refugees need, it was providing the Syrian refugees in case of need (Irq-28EMH- Micro-Syr- M –No.28).

Some refugees note that they have received no assistance from the organizations and actors, except for one time, or what they received was little. A Syrian refugee says,

No organizations have helped since we entered until now, but there was assistance from the local population, especially with regard to food, large quantities of rice, chicken, and broth/ sauce on the borders, and no one helped us in transportation, we took taxis at our own expense (Irq-4RLM- Micro-Syr- M –No.4).

⁴⁵ Sana Fadel, UNHCR, round table meeting on 12/15/2018.

⁴⁶ Hadeel Muhammad, Ibid

Another refugee added in this regard,

I faced the daunting troubles on my own until I could admit one of my children into the hospital. No one helped me except some churches that gave us a food portions (Irq-3OMK- Micro-Syr- M –No.3).

Another refugee says,

After we got into Iraqi territory, I got help from a resident of the villages we passed through, but no organization gave any help (Irq-5HFM- Micro-Syr- M –No.5).

A Syrian female refugee says

No organization provided us with any support, except for the UN, which gave us food and clothes for the children. (Irq-10ARJ- Micro-Syr- F –No.10)

A refugee expressed his complaint, saying,

No organization has provided me with any help, but nine months later we got from Hammurabi Organization for Human Rights a share of detergents. Then, Qandil organization gave us an amount of 465,000 Iraqi dinars. There were people who took more, it turned out it was my bad luck, some people took 935,000 Iraqi dinars. (Irq-1HFK- Micro-Syr- M –No.1)

The army, traffic police, and peshmerga have contributed to transporting and securing ways of transportation for refugees from the borders to the camps, as well as international organizations that have contributed to receiving and transporting refugees. IOM played a vital role in organizing easy, safe, and humane immigration through transporting refugees from the borders to camp and other locations. Friends of Childhood Organization also participated in providing complementary education in Anbar, and the UNHCR had a distinct role in supporting the federal government and the Kurdistan Regional Government in establishing refugee camps and paying the salaries of Syrian teachers who have taught in Al-Qaim camps. I.S.H.O had a prominent role in assisting refugees in Ramadi. The Hammurabi Human Rights Organization has also contributed to providing aid, such as detergents and food baskets, to refugees and displaced people outside the camps.

In this regard, Mr. Ahmed Bassem Mohamed confirms,

The army undertook transporting them from the borders. They were temporarily housed them in 17 schools in Al-Qaim, by the coordination of the local authorities in the district of Al-Qaim and the authorities in Anbar Governorate, until the establishment of camps for them. Iraqi tribes in Anbar Governorate have greatly contributed in providing food, supplies, blankets and mattresses, beside these, the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement provided of three meals, 300,000 Iraqi dinars per family and 150,000 Iraqi dinars per person.⁴⁷

Mohamed Hantouk also says;

The Iraqi Humanitarian Rescue Organization I.S.H.O has continued to carry out its tasks in assisting Syrian refugees in Al-Qaim camps in Ramadi governorate,

⁴⁷ Ahmad Basim Muhammad, *Ibid*

despite the collapse of state institutions there after the ISIS invasion of Ramadi governorate in 2014.⁴⁸

A female activist, working with organizations dealing with refugees, orders the actors in terms of their role "national state, security authorities, the Ministry of Immigration, the non-governmental international bodies, and then comes the role of the national NGOs and volunteers." (Irq-1DGHY-Meso- F-No.1)

A Syrian refugee says,

The Peshmerga forces were receiving us at the borders, they received us well, they provided us with assistance and there were local residents who provided us with food. We stayed in Domiz camp for a year with my brother in the same tent, then we went to Dar Shakran in Erbil. (Irq-12GAB- Micro-Syr- F –No.12)

Another refugee describes a good welcome, saying,

We were received by the Peshmerga, they provided us a car to take us to Domiz camp, and as soon as we reached the borders we moved by car and the car driver provided us with food and water for free, there were deporting at the borders to any of us. (Irq-14SHRO- Micro-Syr- F –No.14)

Reportedly, the UNHCR has stated that its partners in Iraq at the level of the federal government and the Kurdistan region of Iraq are the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement, National Reconciliation and Implementation Committee, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of Interior, the Ministry of Human Rights, the Office of Immigration and Displacement in the Kurdistan Region.

As for non-governmental organizations, they are partnered with the Agency for Development and Technical Cooperation, Al-Khair Humanitarian Organization, *Association for Cultural DevelopmentS for Civil Society*, Human Rights Association, Civil Development Organization, Iraqi Consulting Engineers Syndicate, Danish Refugee Council, United Relief and Compliance Organization for Development, Happy Family Relief and Development Organization, Haricar Organization, International Medical Corps, International Relief and Development Association, International Rescue Committee, Intersos Organization, Iraqi Council for Human Rights, Iraqi Humanitarian Association for Human Rights, Iraqi Humanitarian Rescue Organization, Iraqi Youth League, International Islamic Relief Organization, Kurdish Human Rights Watch, International Mercy Corps, Millennium Relief and Development Services, Islamic Aid, Norwegian Refugee Council, People's Relief Organization, Kandil Organization, Rafha Organization For Relief and Development, the Reach Foundation, Rebuild Iraq Recruitment Program, the Center for Iraqi Human Revival, Save the Children Federation, the Warka Organization, and the Women's Development and Support Organization.

There are international partners such as the International Committee of the Red Cross, the International Organization for Migration (IOM), and the Swedish Civil Emergency Agency. And others.⁴⁹ Attention to Gender and Vulnerable Persons (persons with disabilities, the elderly, children, patients and pregnant women). A Syrian refugee says,

⁴⁸ Muhammad Hantok, *Ilbid*

⁴⁹ UNHCR: Global Appeal 2014-2015, www.unhcr.org. Op.cit.

We came to Erbil by flying to Erbil Airport, there were no harassment from the police or any other airport authorities in Erbil, in fact it; we were treated very well and with respect, I was honest and frankly with the authorities in Erbil, my mother was tired of flying so they put her in a wheelchair and the checking in process was quick. (Irq-2AFSH- Micro-Syr- F –No.2)

Another refugee says,

We crossed through Simalka border crossing by boat and we were received by the Peshmerga. We arrived in the evening. The Peshmerga were surprised about how we were allowed to cross the borders from the Syrian side. We were well received. There was a special concern for us, because my ill son, so they allowed us to enter because of this and gave us water. We took taxi to a big checkpoint but they did not allow us to enter because we are Syrian refugees, we waited for three hours and begged of them, because of my son's ill-health, suffering from epilepsy. One of the soldiers took pity on us and let us through. He asked one of the cars heading to Sulaimaniyah to give us a ride. The driver took us to Sulaimaniyah and he did not charge us a fee. When we got to Sulaimaniyah, the same driver hired us a taxi to take us to Arbad where there were tents, we were given clothes by the camp's guard, an Asayish, there were a special care of gender and being a woman. (Irq-27RHH- Micro-Syr- F –No.27)

Another woman describes her reception, saying,

When we came, our tragedy began and everything changed, what we heard was one thing, but we experienced another thing. When we arrived, we slept on the ground for two days, we did not get any help or a tent, and did not work, we did not have blankets, the attention was only for the sick and those with special needs... There has been a care for gender in the application procedures (Irq-21PFM- Micro-Syr- F –No.21).

A refugee describes the warm welcome she received after entering Iraqi territory, as she says,

After we entered the Iraqi territories (Kurdistan Region of Iraq), I received special treatment because I had children, the Peshmerga were there receiving us. (Irq-14SHRO- Micro-Syr- F –No.14).

Through the meetings of the field team at the meso level, an official at the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement confirmed,

We take into account the conditions of religious groups and their beliefs when providing care to them up to the point of directing our employees not to wear clothes of a certain colour when dealing with a specific category because of the beliefs of that category towards that colour.⁵⁰

⁵⁰ Mohamed Hantok, Director of the Immigration Department of the Ministry of Displacement and Migration, roundtable meeting on 15/12/2018

An activist in a local civil society organization working with refugee says, "Children are more vulnerable, so we have created projects to mainly support children in terms of health, as well as pregnant women, we also provided birth clinics."

Despite the concern shown by individuals and government agencies for people with special needs and attention to gender, the matter is not without challenges. One of the staffs of a local NGO asserts that

Women face many challenges, for example, when arriving at checkpoints, female searchers may not be available, other challenges lie in the absence of detention places or safe places, as for unaccompanied children, UNICEF is the body that is concerned with those children. When an unaccompanied child arrives to a border crossing, he's immediately referred to UNICEF where they are provided with accommodation, safe zones, and education according to a special rehabilitation program.⁵¹

A UNHCR staff member working in Baghdad adds "We have staff members assigned to tackle such challenges. Security authorities detains unaccompanied children in juvenile centres. We have a project to provide protection and legal papers for them. We intervene if the unaccompanied child is arrested."⁵²

4.5. Access to Services:

Most refugees did not receive legal advice or other services such as language lessons or training and vocational courses. Some Syrian refugees confirmed that they received vocational courses and workshops held in their camps or areas of residence, and that participation was optional. Some other stated that they could not participate in vocational training and courses, although available, either because of their preoccupation with their families and children, or their continued engagement with work.

In this regard, a Syrian refugee confirms, "Nobody provided any assistance to me or my children in education." She added, "Vocational courses were held in the camp, such as sewing courses and hairdressing, but I did not attend, I am sick and I have young children to care of." (Irq-18MYA - Micro-Syr- F –No.18)

Another Syrian refugee says, "From the time I arrived until I got an asylum seeker document, I did not get legal advice or any other care from anyone. My children are in a regular school" (Irq-19EMS - Micro-Syr- M –No.19). As a refugee says,

I attended a three-day training course for health installation in the camp conducted by an organization whose name I do not know, some of its staff were Iraqis and others were foreigners, we benefited from the training, we were given a certificate and we gained experience. There are courses but it is not easy to join them, because there is favouritism. The Syrian Mukhtar [supervising and liaising elderly] plays a role choosing participants. There are many courses, attending these courses is free of charge. (Irq-24KJK - Micro-Syr- M –No.24).

⁵¹ Hadeel Muhammad, Ibid

⁵² Sana Fadel UNHCR, Ibid

A refugee describes access to vocational courses, saying,

I took a blacksmithing course and was given a certificate. There were courses, but accessing them is difficult, depends on connections. Attendance at the courses was optional (Irq-29 MSRR- Micro-Syr- M No.29).

Regarding the quality of reception practices, the head of the Immigration Department at the Ministry of Displacement and Migration says,

There is a big map in each camp that points out the services that can be obtained, the procedures to be followed, and the organizations that are concerned with providing them.⁵³

An employee at UNHCR asserts that "Various organizations distribute guidance brochures inside the camps and are available to all"⁵⁴. An official in the UIMS, (an Iraqi NGO) stresses,

Reception practices differ according to the differences in camp managements. Camp management takes into consideration social relationship when distributing tents to the arrivals. It is also concerned with providing tents for service providing organizations, such as medical services, as each organization has an office in the camps and provides phone numbers to facilitate communication 24 hours a day.⁵⁵

4.6. Job opportunities

Through fieldwork and meetings at the level of decision makers and refugees themselves, it became clear that refugees who entered Iraq with the exception of the Kurdistan region were not granted the right to work formally because they were not given the official residency document that they were not considered refugees; rather, they were considered as Syrians displaced across the border.

The Iraqi authorities turned a blind eye to those working in sympathy with their situation, especially those who have been permitted by the security authorities to reside outside the camps, after obtaining sponsorship from well-known Iraqis or in deference to the interests of well-known companies, hotels, and restaurants from the private sector.

As for those inside the camps in the district of Al-Qaim, of Al-Anbar Governorate, the refugees were able to work inside the camps in haircutting, sewing, blacksmithing, construction, and grocery among others. They were not allowed to work outside the camp.⁵⁶

As for the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, most of the refugees expressed that their reception period was short, sometimes not more than few days, and at most a few months. The authorities in the region gave them freedom to leave the camps after being sponsored by

⁵³ Mohamed Hantokllbid , round table meeting, December 15, 2018.

⁵⁴ Sana Fadel, Ibid.

⁵⁵ Hadeel Muhammad, Ibid.

⁵⁶ Ahmed Bassem Mohamed, Ibid.

an Iraqi or by relatives in the region who have had residency or were known to the security authorities.

The authorities in the region also gave the right to work for those who obtained the protection document from the Office of the UNHCR as an asylum seeker, then residency permit. Often, the two documents were obtained within a short time ranging from one to seven months, some have obtained them within a few days or a few weeks after arrival.

Most of the Syrian refugees in Iraq, especially those residing in the Kurdistan region of Iraq who account for up to 96% of the refugees, work in cafes, restaurants, hotels, construction, bakeries and other professions, those without skills worked in cleaning, guarding, and daily wage work.

Many Syrian refugees have been able to find casual or temporary work in the growing economy of Kurdistan, but they still rely heavily on the aid provided by the Iraqi Kurdistan government and international NGOs, especially those who live in the camps. A Syrian refugee says,

When I arrived in Erbil, I worked in Lebanese tourist bakery as a production manager. I worked for two months and I lived above the workplace because it is forbidden to live in a house unless you have a family. I sent a visa to my family. They flew from Damascus airport to Erbil July 10th 2017. I stayed for 3 days with my family in a hotel room in Ainkawa, then I rented a house in Kasnazan because renting a house in Ainkawa costs 400,000 Iraqi Dinars while here [Kasnazan] it costs only 200,000 Iraqi Dinars. After the referendum that took place in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, I was unemployed for 10 months as 446 companies left Erbil, I was about to sign a contract with a Lebanese medical equipment maintenance company with a good salary but they left. During the blockade, I was looking for any work opportunity even as a guard. I received aid from the United Nations only once. When I moved to the camp, we used to get a food ration from the Society of Jesus Friends every 45 days – its president is Dr Rabie. I was unemployed until the May of 2018, I could only do voluntary works for free. Then I was given a job at the reception of hotel. (Irq-3OMK- Micro-Syr- M –No.3)

Another refugee says;

Previously, before I came to Iraq, I was the head of a mould-making carpentry workshop. I have been unemployed for a year now. After I came to Iraq, I met a contractor by chance in a café in the camp and worked for him for six months, Iraqis would come to the camp in case they needed workers. It took me about six or seven months to find work. The job was consistent with my skills. I felt comfortable with this job despite the difficulties of finding work. I did not seek anyone to find job. (Irq-19EMS - Micro-Syr- M –No.19.)

A Syrian refugee describes her experience with work,

Currently, I am a housewife and I do not work. After my marriage, three years ago, that is in 2016, I left work. Before that I used to work in Erbil and worked in several humanitarian organizations such as the Child Welfare Organization and for people with special needs. I got a job through advertisements in the camp, I got a job after one year. I submitted my CV and I was contacted. I was very comfortable with this job. I did not face obstacles in finding work. I did not face

any violations such as harassment. Such things do not exist specially with the presence of Asayish [security and intelligent forces]. (Irq-21PFM - Micro-Syr- F –No.21.)

As another refugee says,

I do not work, I'm a housewife, I did not work in the host country, but I previously worked in agriculture, I was the farm warden, I looked for job but was unsuccessful in finding one, my husband has a regular job. (Irq-27RHH - Micro-Syr- F –No.27.)

A refugee says,

I work in a cafeteria making juices, sweets and cake, I used to work in a shop or cafeteria in Syria. I personally searched for work and it took me two months to get one. I had no problems getting work, sometimes I call on my friends to find me a job, there were no violations or problems at work for me". (Irq-25AWH- Micro-Syr- M –No.25)

Some Syrian refugees expressed their dismay about jobs. They were complaining about the difficulty in obtaining one, because many of them do not know how to access job opportunities, often because they do not know the Kurdish language, so those who know the language were preferred over others. Some of them have also faced discrimination or exploitation in terms of the wages they were getting. They complained that they often receive much lower monthly wages than the Iraqi workers or other Lebanese or Turkish workers. In this regard, a Syrian refugee says,

I worked in a profession other than mine, the job was not compatible with my education, but I worked because of lack of options. I have problems getting a job, a Syrian who does not speak Kurdish is not preferred. (Irq-HFK- Micro-Syr- M – No.1.)

A Syrian refugee confirms that he was subjected to exploitation "I faced difficulties in working with a Turkish contractor as he did not give me my full wages, and he left to Turkey while he owed me \$500." Another Syrian refugee expresses his suffering in finding work in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, saying,

I have difficulty finding work, I go to factories, but if you are not known or go without someone's recommendation, you will not be hired. Initially, it took me five months to find work, which I found through a relative's recommendation. Currently, I have been unemployed for two years." (Irq-29MSRR- Micro-Syr- M – No.29.)

After ISIS invaded many areas in Iraq, which led to the increase in the number of Iraqi displaced people, there were fewer job opportunities for Syrian refugees as Iraqis were being displaced themselves and competing for the same jobs. As a refugee asserts

Now, the situation has changed from what it was previously in terms of the treatment of Syrians and the reason may be the competition for work." (Irq-20RKA- Micro-Syr- M –No.20.)

As a refugee says,

The reception was good, I felt safe and comfortable since I arrived in Kurdistan, but I faced difficulties in finding a job, I stayed for a long time without job due to the war with ISIS and low job opportunities... As for work, I currently work on daily

wages, before that I worked in a construction contracting company (New Zakho) for a year until the end of 2016, since then, I have been working as a day laborer... I suffered a lot of because of unemployment, it took me a long time to find work through my friends, they were working in the same company, the job is compatible with my skills, I also feel comfortable in my work. (Irq-23ASHA- Micro-Syr- M – No.23.)

Another refugee says,

I'm a day laborer, I work one day, and nothing for the next twenty days. In the last three months, I have worked only for two days. Two years ago, jobs were available, but after 2014, work opportunities decreased because of the large number of refugees. Here, you either join the peshmerga and get a salary of 250,000 Iraqi Dinars or remain on the sidewalk. I go out to the workers square until employers come to us, if they don't, I stay till the evening and go back home without work. There are a lot of graduates working as labourer. Most of the job opportunities do not match my skills, I am a construction worker, and other than construction is not compatible with my skills, I am not comfortable when I can't find a job, but I feel comfortable when working, I face obstacles in finding work because there is little opportunity. The help in finding work comes when I ask a friend; they are the ones who help me, they call me when they find me a job (Irq-24KJK- Micro-Syr- M –No.24.) .

5. Conclusions and policy recommendations

When the Syrian crisis started in 2011, Iraq witnessed the return of many Iraqi refugees, especially from Syria, and these returnees were often unable to return to their original locations.⁵⁷ The armed conflict in Anbar Governorate reignited on December 20, 2013, between government forces and the local population, causing the displacement of approximately 500,000 people to other areas inside or outside Anbar Governorate, between January 2014 to September 2014.⁵⁸ On June 10, 2014, ISIS occupied Mosul City⁵⁹, displacing more than a million and a half Iraqis, including hundreds of thousands of minorities, including Chaldeans, Assyrians, Yazidis, Shabaks, Kakayen, and others.

All of these events, which caused the displacement of millions of Iraqis, have caused confusion among the Iraqi institutions. Facing with unprecedented number of refugees and IDPs, governmental authorities both at national and regional levels, civil society organizations, and international organizations did have serious problems in providing adequate reception services. This was partly related to the lack of preparedness, but also to the lack of financial allocations in the Iraqi public budget to accommodate the needs of this size of displacement. Although Iraq has included in its budget allocations for emergencies, these allocations were not sufficient to cover the crisis.

As mentioned, there were challenges at the level of the legal system, as the legal framework did not include a comprehensive law to regulate the conditions of refugees, nevertheless Iraq has a political refugee law and ministry of immigration and displacement law, and both laws lack the process for the refugee reception. Therefore, in order to avoid the shortage, Iraq relied on issuing decisions and instructions fit with the current conditions and issued mainly by the council of ministers and the ministry of immigration and displaced, as well as relying on the mechanisms of international organizations in that, especially the mechanisms and rules followed by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees.

Iraq has also faced challenges since the initial reception of Syrian refugees entering through the Al-Qa'im port located in the west of the country in Al-Anbar Governorate. As a result of its lack of camps and centers prepared for receiving, which forced the refugees to be placed in government school buildings that lack the most basic necessities of life, some considered it a prison. Government officials have considered this to be a failure to receive refugees.⁶⁰

Iraq also faced health challenges since the initial reception of Syrian refugees at the border. It has been proven by a number of doctors that most of the refugees who come to the medical unit are suffering from various digestive diseases or skin allergies. They also diagnosed cases of scabies, The patients were handled according to the well-known healthcare rules applied in primary health care programs⁶¹, and some of the refugees were

⁵⁷ Global appeal, 2014-2015, www.unhcr.org

⁵⁸ World Report 2015, Iraq events, 2014 www.hrw.org...15/country-chapters/268122

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ Video / Al Jazeera TV channel, Al Jazeera Arabic on 07/26/2012

⁶¹ Anbar Health Department report, directorate of Al-Qaem sector for Primary health care, Syrian refugee camps, issued on 01/08/2012.

infected with viral hepatitis, and they were referred to the existing hospital and their numbers were few.⁶²

Also we can infer that the experiences of those who seek asylum, and are given refugee status, are not the same. Their impressions about the quality of their experience, from the moment they entered into Iraq or its region of Kurdistan, depended on those who interacted with them. The recipient authority or stakeholder matters in the subjective perception of reception in general. If the person receiving and registering the refugees and IDPs was sympathetic to their plight, they felt more more welcomed. Obviously, the existence of such individuals can make huge difference in the course of reception, preparing paperwork, living in the camps, leaving to urban areas, getting training opportunities or finding jobs.

Based on this impression we can recommend that we might be able to change a lot without incurring huge costs by creating the right attitudes and sympathy for asylum seekers and refugees in local officials or peoples or to work in order to assign those officials to carry out works with asylum seekers and refugees who are sympathetic.

A second clear observation is that there are limitations in terms of housing, training, job opportunities. The recommendation here would be to work to improve the economic condition in Iraq or inject funds by international organizations to improve housing and provide training to refugees.

Thirdly, refugees spoke about the role of individual connections and patronage. Such problems are also suffered by all Iraqis. Although, refugees would suffer much more from such problems than local people do, considering that once uprooted, immigrants lose most of the leverages they enjoy in their home countries. The recommendation here would be to have influential dignitaries and NGOs intervening continuously on behalf of refugees.

The experiences of the asylum seekers and refugees also depended on the conditions of areas or regions in Iraq that hosted them. Kurdistan Region seems to have been preferred considering its relative safety and security and better economy. However, it is also clear the period before Daesh (ISIS) and Referendum were better than the period following those two turning points in the areas. So it could be recommended that the engagement of the international community in keeping stability as well as advising moderate policies and abstaining from adventurism will bring about security and prosperity for the local populations as well as the immigrants or refugees.

To bring hope and restore dignity for most of refugees who are currently trapped within camps is to help them find jobs, which requires meaningful training that lead to employability or starting business. Also, Iraq witnessed sectarian conflict in 2006-2007, and displacement of thousands and even millions from conflict areas to safer areas, especially the Kurdistan region of Iraq, in addition to that the flow of Syrian refugees to the Kurdistan region of Iraq at the beginning of the crisis in 2011, which gave the Kurdistan region experience in dealing with the issue of receiving refugees as well as adequate infrastructure to handle refugee flows and receive them appropriately. This experience

⁶² Ahmed Bassem Mohamed, Ibid.

also lead to cooperation with the Iraqi government institutions and international organizations such as UNHCR and IOM in receiving refugees.

Policy recommendations

For greater and closer regulation, we recommend the following:

- **Geneva Convention on Protection of Refugees:** Iraq should join the International Refugee Convention of 1951 and its amended Protocol of 1967.
- **A Comprehensive Legislation:** Legislation of the refugee's laws should include rules for a reception as soon as possible.
- **A coordination framework:** A comprehensive coordination framework should be created between the agencies operating in reception, whether between institutions of the federal government and those in the Kurdistan region of Iraq or between local and international organizations among themselves and made joint working groups improve performance in reception.
- **Housing:** Economic conditions in Iraq should be improved by international organizations injecting funds to improve housing and provide training to refugees.
- **International Community:** International community should be more engaged in keeping stability as well as advising moderate policies and abstaining from adventurism to bring about security and prosperity for the local populations as well as the immigrants or refugees.

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7. Appendices

Table.1 The actual interviews for Syrian refugees:

Province	2014-2017 Arrival Date	2011-2014 Arrival Date	Ethnic Religious Minorities	Female No.	Male No.	Interviews #
Baghdad	5	1	2	3	3	6
Erbil	5	1	2	4	2	6
Dohuk	6	1	3	3	4	7
Sulaimaniya	3	1	2	2	2	4
Najaf	2	-	-	1	1	2
Babel	2	-	-	1	1	2
Karbala	2	-	-	1	1	2
Total	25	4	9	15	14	29

The actual interviews with Syrian refugees:

Refugees by age group are divided into three categories according to the above table data

(18-38years), (9) male interview, (8) female interview.

(39-59 years), (5) male interview, (4) female interview.

(60 - More) (2) male interview, (1) female interview.

Table.2 The actual interviews for IDPs

Province	2014-2017 Arrival Date	2011-2014 Arrival Date	Ethnic Religious Minorities	Female No.	Male No.	No. of Interviews
Baghdad	5	1	2	3	3	6
Erbil	5	1	2	4	2	6
Dohuk	6	1	3	3	4	7
Sulaimaniya	3	1	2	2	2	4
Najaf	2	-	-	1	1	2
Babel	2	-	-	1	1	2
Karbala	2	-	-	1	1	2
Total	25	4	9	15	14	29

IDPs by age group are divided into three categories according to the above table data (18-38 years), (5) male interview, (6) female interview.
(39 - 59 years), (6) male interview, (8) female interview.
(60 - More) (3) Male interview, (1) female interview.

Figure 1 : The copy of a pledge (commitment)

بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم
 جمهورية العراق
 رقم الاستمارة (٠٥٠)

**الجمهورية العراقية
 لجنة تسليم اللاجئين السوريين
 الى الكفلا**

تعهد

أقر الموقع أنه ()
 الممثل في منطقة ()
 بالمحافظة الموصلين المدرجة أسماهم أدناه وفق الشروط التالية اذ ان كافة المستندات بخلاف تلك المحمل تحق
 الاكراهات القانونية والآلية والتي تاريخ (/ / ٢٠١٢)
 ١ - تم تزويد جواز السفر واللقب الذي سبق خلال ٢١ ساعة
 ٢ - تم تزويد اسم العائلة باسمه الذي المتعلق بالحقائق الشخصية لكل من العائلة واللقب العرفي
 ٣ - التحمل بالان يكون متفهم، غير متحيز، في تكيفات اقليمية ولم يكن متفهميا للتحكم السوري.
 ٤ - التحمل الرامة لتأثيره فيها (١٠٠٠٠٠٠) شجرة مائتين مزارع من تد يود تأخير في حلة استعادة مفقود.
 ٥ - ان يكون المتفهم ضمن الرقعة الجغرافية لمنطقة سكنه ولا يسمح له بالانطلاق الى المحافظات الاخرى.

ت	الاسم الرباعي واللقب	الجنس	تاريخ الميلاد	رقم المستند	الملاحظات
١					
٢					
٣					
٤					
٥					
٦					
٧					
٨					
٩					

الاسم الرباعي واللقب الكامل:
 الكفر الكامل:
 رقم الهاتف:
 صلة القرابة:
 لجنة استشارات سورية شرقية تقدم
 المستقر
 الجهة المرجعية

مفكرة المفكرات
 مفكرة الامن الوطني
 يمكن انتمى ٠١

الجهة الاقليمية في المجلس الوطني للتقدم
 مفكرة اللقب العرفي

التفويض
 ارحمن كيدان فرحان
 كهدمقدم تقدم القيد
 الحريق ارحمن
 المجلس ارحمن ارحمن
 يمكن المجلس الامن الوطني

ملاحظة: تزود نسخة توثيقة من المستندات الشخصية لتتفق مع التجه

Figure 2 : The translated version of the (commitment)

In the name of God the Compassionate, the Merciful

Republic Of Iraq

District Commissioner of Al-Qaem

Form No. (050)

Syrian Refugee Transfer Committee

To the Sponsors

Commitment

I, the undersigned below ()

Resident in the region () I guarantee for keeping the Syrian citizens whose names are listed below, according to the following conditions before all authorities. Otherwise, I carry all legal procedures and for which I signed on / / 2012

- 1- It is obligatory to bring the sponsored person on request within 24 hours.**
- 2 -It is obligatory for the state that the sponsored person not to carry out sabotage activities that violate state security and public order.**
- 3 -I pledged that the sponsored person was not affiliated with terrorist organizations and was not required by the Syrian courts.**
- 4- I shall bear a delay fine of (10000000) ten million dinars for each day of delay in the event of summoning the sponsored.**
- 5- The sponsored person must be within the geographical area of my residential area and not allowed to move to other provinces.**

Series	Name and Surname	Sex	Date of Birth	No. of Document	Notes
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					

8					
9					
10					
11					
12					
13					
14					
15					

Name and Surname of the sponsor:

Full address:

Telephone number:

Relationship:

Intelligence Division of the The Mayor of locality Recommending authority
Police Directorate of the district

Intelligence Department National Security Office Representative of Army Brigade28

Security Committee of the District Council for Judicial Department Notary Public

The Judge Farhan Qutaikhan Farhan Lt. Gen.
District Mayer Mohsen Abdul Hasan Lazim
Of Al- Qaem National Security Council representative

Note: A color copy of the sponsor's personal documents is attached to the Commitment